

Safe and Sustainable by Design:
Topline results of a SAbyNA survey of social representations among 172 members of the international nanotechnology community

Claire Mays, Fanny Karatchodjoukova, and Sean Hardy

Report on RRI Study 2 including inputs for SAbyNA communications and for European-level reflection.
Deliverable 8.5 of the SAbyNA.eu project

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SABYNA Simple, robust and cost-effective approaches to guide industry in the development of safer nanomaterials and nano-enabled products

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Mays Claire, Karatchodjoukova Fanny, and Hardy Sean

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Abstract

The Responsible Research and Innovation team of Horizon 2020 Project SAbyNA in 2023 performed a large anonymous survey (N=172) of how the nanotechnology and advanced materials communities conceive of “Safe and Sustainable by Design” (SSbD). Empirical social psychology methods and concepts were employed to benchmark so-called social representations of SSbD during a period when this strategic approach is undergoing rapid mindful development. Expert stakeholders were invited to share their implicit definitions, agreement or disagreement on selected facets of achieving nanosafety and sustainability. This SAbyNA deliverable presents methodology, topline findings, and some interpretative analysis. A comparison is performed with pilot findings collected in 2021 (n=164; Hardy & Mays 2022). Results show increasing complexity of SSbD concepts within the community. Preventive safety strategies emerge as a frame for considering materials and processes, and as a driving force to achieve “One Health”-type outcomes. Environmental aspects of sustainability are foremost in mind but a strong desire to develop socio-economic aspects is clear. An SSbD community culture emerges, characterized by the conviction that SSbD will improve environmental health and occupational safety. Participants recognize that SSbD induces a new mentality and are highly engaged. While they agree that SSbD will not hinder innovation, views on operational challenges including cost are more scattered. We identify these less settled attitudes as needing discussion and debate. We briefly report four workshops in which members of the European and international nano communities have engaged with the survey data. We suggest that the survey results can support interdisciplinary, cross-sector stakeholder dialogue, consolidate the community, and facilitate access to improved SSbD guidance (such as that offered by the SAbyNA online guidance platform). Background literature and advanced survey analysis will be detailed in a future peer-reviewed publication.

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Table of Contents

Abstract	2
Acknowledgements	2
Citation	2
Executive Summary – Survey Findings and Utility.....	5
1. Introduction: Opening a new window on Safe and Sustainable by Design	7
1.1 A good time to explore SSbD.....	9
1.2 Why study social representations?.....	10
1.3 Our starting hypothesis – and our present end state	11
2. The SAbyNA RRI Study Methodology	13
2.1 The questionnaire	13
2.1.1 Free associations	13
2.1.2 Topical statements (Agree/Disagree).....	14
2.1.3 Demography	15
2.2 The co-constructive workshops.....	15
2.3 Recruiting respondents.....	16
3. Results and Discussion.....	18
3.1 Obtained sample	18
3.2 Demographics	18
3.2.1 Geographic location	19
3.2.2 Sector of activity	19
3.2.3 Primary disciplinary field of training	20
3.2.4 Involvement in a government sponsored-project.....	20
3.3 Free associations	21
3.3.1 Data coding categories and frequencies	21
3.3.2 “Safe by Design”	21
3.3.3 “Sustainability”	23
3.3.4 Mapping predominant relations between associations – at two periods.....	25
3.4 Topical aspects of Safe and Sustainable by Design.....	30
3.4.1 Consensus items – Supermajority agreement.....	30
3.4.2 Dispersion/ dissensus, or ambiguous responses	32
3.4.3 Not applicable or no judgment formed.....	33
3.4.4 “What did we miss?”	33
3.5 Co-constructive workshops: Community reflections	36
3.5.1 Venice NanoSafety Training School	36
3.5.2 NanoSAFE ‘23 Conference	38
3.5.3 SAbyNA 42-Month Consortium Meeting.....	38
3.5.4 JRC/PARC SSbD Bootcamp	39
4. Conclusions and Perspectives.....	42
4.1 Main messages of the SAbyNA survey.....	42
4.2 An expanding cultural dynamic.....	43
4.3 Dialogue and guidance for SSbD progress	45
4.4 Future prospects: benchmarking and systematic research.....	46

References.....	47
Annex: The SAbyNA Responsible Research and Innovation questionnaire on social representations of Safe and Sustainable by Design.....	49

List of Boxes

Box 1. SAbyNA is a European Commission-funded Horizon 2020 project.....	7
Box 2. “SSbD could be applied across numerous technologies”.....	8
Box 3. The European Commission Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS).....	10
Box 4. “Safe by Design” Free Associations Codebook (labels and category contents).....	21
Box 5. “Sustainability” Free Associations Codebook (labels and category contents).....	23
Box 6. Interdisciplinarity and dialogue between stakeholders.....	44

List of Tables

Table I. Statements about SSbD organized by thematic bloc chosen at survey design stage. (*Item reversed for analysis.).....	14
Table II. Statements dominated by swing opinions (“somewhat agree” or “somewhat disagree”). Rounded percentages of response.....	32
Table III. Dissensus statements.....	33
Table IV. Statements on which no judgment is formed.....	33
Table V. Respondents’ suggestions for additional survey items, coded on Safe by Design free association categories and grouped.....	35
Table VI. Top three priority statements selected by NanoSAFE ’23 workshop participants.....	38

List of Figures

Figure 1. Social media image inviting survey participation before the Venice NanoSafety Training School. ..	16
Figure 2. Social media images inviting survey participation by the global community.....	17
Figure 3. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by region in which they work.....	19
Figure 4. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by professional sector.....	19
Figure 5. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by primary discipline.....	20
Figure 6. Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term “Safe by Design” (N _{associations} =537, from 172 participants).....	22
Figure 7. Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term “Sustainability” (N _{associations} =549, from 172 participants).....	24
Figure 8. 2021- Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term “Safe by Design” (N _{associations} = 456, from 164 participants in Hardy & Mays 2022).....	26
Figure 9. Linkages observed between categories of free associations to the term “Safe by Design” in 2021 (from 164 respondents) and in 2023 (from 172 respondents).....	26
Figure 10. Linkages observed between categories of free associations to the term “Sustainability” in 2023 (from 172 respondents).....	28
Figure 11. Consensus statements enjoying a supermajority (≥60%) of agreement. Ordered by rounded % of overall agreement in descending order.....	30
Figure 12. Categorization of respondents’ proposed additional items or commentary (N=44, from 172 participants).....	34
Figure 13. Discussion questions from the SAbyNA RRI workshop at Venice NanoSafety Training School (using interim survey results, May 2023).....	37
Figure 14. Conceptual cluster best aligned with JRC/PARC Bootcamp participants’ personal conception of SSbD or of Sustainability.....	40
Figure 15. Topical statements about SSbD developed for the JRC/PARC Bootcamp; participants’ agreement or disagreement (N=32; frequencies).....	41

Executive Summary – Survey Findings and Utility

In the domain of nanotechnologies, safety and sustainability can be anticipated and actuated from the earliest stages of development of new particles and advanced materials, nano-enabled products, and Research & Innovation activities. In Europe and abroad such an approach is called **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)**. The early 2020s see an accelerating movement by academia, government, and industry towards definition, operationalization, and application of SSbD concepts and strategies. With such a dynamic in full swing, it is a good time to survey the nano communities. Study in this seminal period can capture areas of controversy and ideas in transition, and benchmark the SSbD culture.

In 2023, the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) team of the Horizon 2020 SAbyNA project¹ performed a large anonymous survey (N=172) of how the nanotechnology and advanced materials communities conceive of SSbD. Using empirical social psychology methods, so-called social representations of SSbD were captured during this period of rapid mindful development. Expert stakeholders shared their implicit definitions and agreement or disagreement on selected facets of achieving nanosafety and sustainability. This deliverable report details methodology, topline findings, and some interpretative analysis. A comparison is performed with pilot findings collected in 2021 (n=164; Hardy & Mays 2022²). We briefly report four workshops in which members of the European and international nano communities engaged with the survey data. Background literature and advanced survey analysis will be presented in a future peer-reviewed publication.

Consensus results include:

- SSbD concepts across the community are increasing in complexity. Preventive safety strategies emerge as a frame for considering materials and processes, and as a driving force to achieve “One Health”-type outcomes.
- Environmental aspects of sustainability are foremost in mind, but participants strongly express the need to develop socio-economic aspects, as well as to extend awareness and discussion of SSbD across the stakeholder landscape.
- An interdisciplinary, cross-sectoral SSbD community culture emerges, characterized by a “supermajority” conviction that SSbD will improve the health of the environmental and occupational safety, and that it must be introduced preventively. Participants recognize that SSbD induces a new mentality, and they call for guidance tools and resources. They are highly engaged.

Combined with field observations, these consensus results reveal an enthusiastic dynamic of knowledge development, in a diverse community bound together by a common action goal.

¹ SAbyNA.eu is a European Commission-funded Horizon 2020 project entitled “*Simple, robust and cost-effective approaches to guide industry in the development of safer nanomaterials and nano-enabled products*”. SAbyNA proposes a digital guidance platform delivering SSbD tools and strategies to maximize nanosafety and sustainability while maintaining the functionality gained by incorporating nanomaterials.

² Hardy S & Mays C (2022) Safe by Design: Fostering interdisciplinary dialogue. Findings, methods, materials. SAbyNA deliverable report D8.3, 26pp. Institut Symlog de France, Paris.
<https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.7319123>

Findings are similar across all declared disciplines and sectors. This cultural dynamic, combined with the stakeholders' demonstrated willingness to communicate across lines, should be recognized as particular strengths for reaching the goals of SSbD.

The SAbyNA RRI survey also revealed the below areas in which social representations are not strongly fixed:

- While participants agree that SSbD will not hinder innovation, their views on operational challenges are more scattered.
- Dissensus is seen regarding whether SSbD can be implemented across industrial contexts, and the impacts that will be felt.
- In particular, no clear trend of understanding emerges regarding the costs associated with SSbD.

How can such data serve the community? The SAbyNA RRI survey results single out aspects for which further dialogue, operationalization, and guidance are needed to effectively apply SSbD. They are also aspects for which some objective guidance does exist and where stakeholders can be given more foresight. They should be mindfully examined and debated in the next development period, to reinforce the joint dynamic by which the uncertainties are reduced.

The SAbyNA guidance platform addresses certain of these problematic aspects directly. Stakeholders could join a cross-sector workshop to debate the weakest survey consensus items: *"I have a good overall understanding of how SSbD at my own level impacts other parts of the value chain,"* and *"SSbD will require lots of changes to industrial processes."* They could examine the divergent and unclear views on SSbD's costs and impacts. This dialogue could be followed immediately by a hands-on learning application of the SAbyNA online tool. Indeed, the SAbyNA guidance platform delivers quantified, operational replies to questions on the costs and requirements of improving safety and sustainability, through comparing detailed nano/advanced materials, product or process scenarios. The SAbyNA platform provides to industrial stakeholders (particularly in the nano-enabled paints and additive manufacturing sectors) a tailored response to the still-unclear issues of the magnitude of costs potentially added by SSbD, and the compatibility of the approach within their production environment.

At the present time, the survey results are useful because they can spark dialogue and objectively highlight areas where guidance can and must provide pragmatic responses. In this way, the SAbyNA RRI study seeks to enrich the current discourse on SSbD and promote a supportive context for innovation and interdisciplinarity.

The SAbyNA survey results also have a future value. The comparison of 2021 and 2023 data furnished some specific insights that may not have emerged at a single-time assessment. Looking forward, the SAbyNA social representations survey contributes a baseline for continued measurement of the evolution of expert views and practices across future years. This image of experts' understanding of SSbD at today's point in time may also serve when later, the eventual uptake in broader European and consumer society of ideas about Safe and Sustainable by Design is traced and assessed.

1. Introduction: Opening a new window on Safe and Sustainable by Design

Manufactured nanomaterials have long entered our daily lives, with applications ranging from consumer products to electronics, from clean energy components to medical uses. Science, government, and industry have embraced the need for assessment, prevention, and cost-effective mitigation of any risks to health and the environment, at every point in product life cycles. With growing knowledge and means to translate it into decisions and processes, safety and sustainability can be anticipated and actuated from the earliest stages of development of new particles and advanced materials, nano-enabled products, and Research & Innovation activities. In Europe and abroad such an approach is called **Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)**.

Developing nanotechnology engages the skills of diverse professional sectors, inside the broad context of the green transition, consumer demands, and regulatory governance. Recent years have seen significant, concerted efforts by academia, government, and industry to formalize and implement SSbD concepts. Deeply involved actors describe SSbD as a paradigm shift. Some stakeholders by contrast point to an extension of longtime industrial innovation practices where safety, and sustainability on certain criteria, have always been paramount constraints. Other images or attitudes as well - positive, skeptical, or neutral - may be found, translating diverse views on SSbD's aims, promises, requirements, and perspectives for action.

The SAbyNA project (see Box 1) includes a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) activity (cf. v. Schomberg 2013) that opens a thoughtful window on this complex environment. Using empirical social psychology methods and concepts, the SAbyNA RRI team aims to **benchmark what we call social representations of SSbD in the diverse nano community**³. Expert stakeholders are invited to look together at how today they implicitly define, agree, or disagree on selected facets of achieving nanosafety and sustainability. Simple survey data can reveal whether ideas about SSbD and its implications are widely shared, or potentially disparate - even in the case of some ideas that might “go without saying”.

Box 1. SAbyNA is a European Commission-funded Horizon 2020 project entitled “*Simple, robust and cost-effective approaches to guide industry in the development of safer nanomaterials and nano-enabled products*”. SAbyNA assembles and reinforces the scientific and practical underpinning of selected SSbD tools and resources (databases and models). It proposes a digital guidance platform delivering Safety by Design strategies that will enable professionals to maximize nanosafety while maintaining the functionality gained by incorporating nanomaterials.

SAbyNA has created an industry user-friendly **platform** with optimized workflows to support the safe development of nanomaterials and nano-enabled products. The online tool operationalizes SSbD in detail, on hazard, exposure, and several sustainability criteria, and provides tailored action

³ We use the terms “nano community” and “communities” loosely at this stage of research, with the consciousness that professionals involved with nanotechnology and/or advanced materials may have diverse backgrounds and standpoints, and differing levels of interaction and contact. As for their possible degree of like-mindedness on certain topical issues discussed in the SSbD area today, this feature of “community” is indeed what our survey attempts to measure.

recommendations, supporting users to implement the iterative European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) SSbD Framework.

The SAbYNA platform offers Safe by Design approaches and risk mitigation measures, along with decision trees to help select the best strategies to protect workers, consumers, and the environment, taking into account life cycle stages. A simplified Life Cycle Analysis module helps assess resource consumption and improve environmental sustainability. Cost calculations help to compare production and use scenarios.

Continuous dialogue with stakeholders and end-users amplifies the added value of the SAbYNA platform for the Additive Manufacturing and Paint sectors. <https://www.sabyna.eu/>

In 2023, we invited professionals across the globe involved with nanotechnology and/or advanced materials to share some of their views on SSbD, using a short online questionnaire touching on a few contentious, high-level issues among the topics commonly discussed today.

- This SAbYNA deliverable report details our social science methodology, our topline findings, and some interpretative analysis.
- We show as well how some members of the European and international nano communities have engaged with our data in workshop conversations.

Our qualitative work intends to support the already greatly developed responsible and interdisciplinary communication taking place within the nano communities. Our aim is to foster local discussion and add to the insights characterizing the constantly evolving SSbD area.

Safety and Sustainability by Design is an approach that could benefit society in numerous technological areas (see Box 2). Our intention has been to provide rigorous, reproducible social science research to foster insight into SSbD and also confidence in how such RRI studies can contribute to safety, sustainability and innovation.

Background literature and advanced analysis will be presented in a future peer-reviewed publication.

Box 2. “SSbD could be applied across numerous technologies”, stated a deliverable reviewer (W.R.N.) who is a nuclear engineer and expert of real-time risk and fault management in high-reliability systems (space and nuclear). “Safety and Sustainability by Design is an excellent concept, and could be used to systematically introduce both safety and sustainability at the beginning of the system life cycle, rather than waiting until after implementation and having to deal with the unintended consequences. **This proactive approach could be applied across numerous technologies to address risks early, for example artificial intelligence.**

“The SSbD concept could also be used to place the definitions and objectives for both safety and sustainability on stronger foundations, leading to broader consensus for approaches to be used and success criteria for both.

“Similarly, the SSbD concept could be used to form the foundation for a common language for communication and consensus across disciplines, organizations, and stakeholder groups.

“Regarding the conduct of rigorous, reproducible RRI studies, improving the integration of social sciences with engineering and operations is important, and this kind of dialogue is very helpful.”

1.1 A good time to explore SSbD

Today in Europe and abroad we witness an accelerating movement towards definition, operationalization, and application of Safe by Design and Sustainable by Design concepts and approaches. This movement is framed by research funding and work programs, and pushed by intensive, continuous collaborative efforts reaching across academia, governmental and international organizations, and industry. These continually evolving efforts posit the need for a “wider SSbD implementation roadmap, which will eventually provide resolutions of nanosafety debates between academia, regulators and industry” (Furxhi et al., 2023).

A look back over the past decade in Europe shows the increasing focus on *Safe by Design* in the area of nanotechnology, and then a rapid five-year expansion to *Safe and Sustainable by Design*. Initiatives by the European Commission (EC) and its Joint Research Centre (JRC), funded Research & Innovation (R&I) projects, industry associations, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), and other regional or international groupings mindfully seek to **build up a shared SSbD culture and resources**. Such initiatives do not address only nanotechnologies and advanced materials, but open a broad vista on safety and sustainability as “core performance functions of the chemicals of the future⁴”.

The variety of efforts, their concerted, consultative, and strongly integrative nature, and their willingness to accommodate a diversity of goals and expectations, make this a good time to survey the nano communities. Study in this seminal period can capture areas of controversy and ideas in transition, and benchmark the SSbD culture. Involved professionals display interest in gaining such reflexive knowledge. Surveying interdisciplinary, intersectoral populations is a method of choice, as illustrated by just two examples:

- In September 2022, representatives of eleven EC-funded SSbD projects and of some highly involved European and international organizations gathered to pinpoint the “status, implications and challenges of European SSbD paradigms applicable to nanomaterials and advanced materials”. They internally surveyed and discussed views on “higher level challenges towards the realistic implementation and dissemination” of SSbD (Furxhi et al., 2023).
- The EC-funded IRISS project “aims to connect, synergize and transform the Safe-and-Sustainable by Design community in Europe and globally”. IRISS surveyed safety design and sustainability practices and principles (Nov. ‘22 - Feb. ‘23), obtaining 86 responses to this collective mapping exercise from organizations in 19 countries.

We elaborated our SAbyNA RRI survey research in 2023. By that time, at least five “main published frameworks” for SSbD were proposed, including those by the European Environment Agency (EEA 2021), the OECD (2022), the European Chemical Industry Council (Cefic 2022) and the International Chemical Secretariat (Chemical Strategy for Sustainability 2020) (cited in IRISS, n.d.). Perhaps that benefitting from the highest visibility is a framework developed in response to the 2020 EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (see Box 3), underlain by an intensive consultation and development process conducted by the JRC. This framework was

⁴ As expressed by the Lowell Center for Sustainable Production during a European Commission Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) consultation on 18 May 2022: <https://webcast.ec.europa.eu/3rd-meeting-of-the-high-level-roundtable-on-the-chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability>.

formally established by the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/2510 of 8 December 2022⁵. The JRC SSbD Framework is presented as a voluntary approach to guide the innovation process for chemicals and materials. It comprises two main stages: chemicals (re)design guided by principles believed to maximize positive safety and sustainability outcomes, followed by assessment, with iteration in each or both stages as needed. Overall criteria are: *maximizing functionality, minimizing hazard and exposure potential, and satisfying environmental impact and cost requirements*. In the present period, the JRC SSbD framework approach is under testing through real-life case studies.

Box 3. The European Commission Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) sets out Safety and Sustainability by Design as a central to production and use of chemicals in the green and digital transition.

The CSS defined SSbD as “**a pre-market approach to chemicals that focuses on providing a function (or service), while avoiding volumes and chemical properties that may be harmful to human health or the environment, in particular groups of chemicals likely to be (eco) toxic, persistent, bio-accumulative or mobile. Overall sustainability should be ensured by minimizing the environmental footprint of chemicals in particular on climate change, resource use, ecosystems and biodiversity from a lifecycle perspective.**” (p4, fn19)

[Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability](#)

1.2 Why study social representations?

The forceful dynamic underway to define, operationalize, and implement SSbD provides a **rich reservoir of ideas and notions**. These are rooted in **specialized knowledge and practice** and, as they are mindfully communicated and discussed, they contribute in turn to **building up shared norms and expectations**.

The SAbYNA RRI team uses the **theory of social representations** from social psychology to observe this dynamic process.

- The intensive European mapping and development activities around the science and the application of SSbD yield an image of the *state of the art*.
- The SAbYNA RRI study outputs a complementary image of how some participants in the dynamic are *constructing the reality* of SSbD, on a social, cultural and psychological level.

The theory of social representations proposes that the members of any given community share a fund of views, meanings, and understandings, constructed through shared practices and communication (Moscovici 2001). These views, meanings, practices, and understandings, called social representations, form part of the fabric of group culture.

Social representations are cognitive, emotional, and performative. Inter alia, they provide illustrations of what Kearnes (2007) called “dreams of nanotechnology and their manifestation and permutation in contemporary research and development” (p. 145).

Whether they remain in the unspoken background or are explicitly discussed, social representations help to transmit and reinforce the culture and identity of the group. Of course,

⁵ COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION (EU) 2022/2510 of 8 December 2022 establishing a European assessment framework for ‘safe and sustainable by design’ chemicals and materials. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reco/2022/2510/oj#document1>

individuals belong to several different communities at the same time, which may not share representations, or whose representations may even sometimes come into conflict. We are interested here in the processes, images and actions by which a diversified professional community may build up a particular shared culture and set of views regarding the object “SSbD” in particular.

The theory of social representations also suggests that over time, through the exchange of knowledge, discussion, and practical activity by community members, their shared specialist representations will eventually diffuse outward towards other stakeholders and/or larger societal spheres (Bauer and Gaskell 2008). In this way, the concerted dynamic seen in e.g. Europe to create a shared understanding and operationalization of SSbD could eventually largely influence the ways European or other publics represent nanotechnologies and advanced materials. The specialist work to make chemicals safer and more sustainable can eventually become part of general culture, and shape expectations and behavior by consumers.

The SAbyNA deliverable report “*Safe by Design: Fostering Interdisciplinary Dialogue. Findings, Methods, Materials*” (Hardy & Mays 2022) highlights nano experts’ social representations of Safe by Design revealed by a pilot mini-survey of 164 persons in Europe and worldwide, conducted in 2021. Using a free association method, our pilot survey captured the words and ideas that are closest to mind at a given time - the **images and meanings** that individuals bring to (and/or have taken from) the common pot, and to which they may assign special importance.

The 2023 survey reported in the present deliverable again uses the free associations method, creating the possibility of comparing representations of Safe by Design at two different points in time, and furthermore gathering imagery associated with Sustainability. The 2023 survey also measures aspects of participants’ **relationships** at this point in time with the SSbD approach, through their familiarity and degree of engagement, and their alignment with common or controversial views on SSbD’s novelty, promises, and barriers.

Stakeholder discussion of the obtained survey results, including consensus and dissensus, can add to the SSbD dynamic. In particular, the cognitive and social phenomena of opinion and belief, touched on in the SAbyNA RRI survey, may be less frequently examined in the everyday practice of SSbD professional stakeholders. Making social representations of SSbD into an object of systematic study and reflection can help to reveal their influence, and support the community in deciding ways forward.

1.3 Our starting hypothesis – and our present end state

In 2015, members of our team used a social representations approach to test whether 163 members of the expert community perceived nanotechnology through the classical “risks/benefits” dichotomy (Bertoldo et al. 2016). We found that disciplinary background revealed differences in the way experts make sense of these new technologies. So-called “upstream” groups, physical scientists and engineers, tended to represent nanotechnologies in terms of opportunities and not in terms of risks. By contrast, “downstream” groups, environmental, life, and social scientists, tended to share a more complex or twofold representation. For these groups, nanotechnologies were interpreted as offering great opportunities but still are accompanied by unknown risks, described at different scales

(material, environmental or societal). Of note, respondent sector did not explain variance in views.

The SAbyNA RRI Team set out in 2020 with the intention to characterize a new set of social representations by the expert nano community: empirical and intuitive definitions and meanings associated with Safe and Sustainable by Design. We expected that, similar to the results of our previous study and of many risk perception studies in other areas, the following hypothesis might be borne out: *disciplinary background underlies observed differences in the representation of SSbD*.

In point of fact, our first analyses of the 2023 SAbyNA data collected from 172 respondents **do not** allow us to say that discipline significantly discriminates attitudes. For this reason, readers will not find a breakdown of results per primary discipline in this topline results report.

We note in passing that several internal reviewers of this deliverable report expressed a lively interest in the influence of professional sector on the gathered SSbD views. Because sector was not discriminant in our earlier research (Bertoldo et al. 2016) we did not formulate a hypothesis on this aspect. Moreover, our 2023 findings do not demonstrate a meaningful distinction of responses according to these features of respondent identity; no breakdown is reported in this deliverable.

- To be clear, our preliminary analyses of data from 172 respondents revealed that no disciplinary or sectoral group differed significantly from the overall mean.
- **This is in itself a finding: the self-selected population sample would, in this manner, appear indeed to constitute a community with shared representations.**
- Section 3 reports and discusses the results, pointing out in particular the representations enjoying a “supermajority” consensus, as well as the areas characterized by dissensus (dispersion of replies) or other lack of consensus – which, we suggest, constitute fruitful areas for community debate and development, and operational guidance.

We intend to re-code discipline (Section 3.2.3), delve into other demographics, and repeat statistical analyses to reveal other relationships internal to the data. Findings will be presented in a future peer-reviewed article. Nonetheless, the qualitative topline results we present here yield very suggestive interpretations of how some social representations of SSbD stand in 2023. We also leverage 2021 pilot study data (Hardy & Mays 2022) to trace subtle evolutions in these representations.

2. The SAbyNA RRI Study Methodology

To gather data on social representations we relied on two parallel and complementary methods: a multi-component anonymous survey questionnaire; and co-constructive community workshops. Personalized email outreach to invite participation in the survey, as well as social media announcements, took place mainly in late March and throughout April 2023. This outreach was periodically renewed in May and June leveraging the dissemination of community newsletters and conference announcements. The online questionnaire administered through the Qualtrics platform gathered answers April-June 2023. Partial, interim results were progressively shared with workshop participants May-October 2023 (without publicizing the results outside these venues, to avoid biasing persons who had not yet filled in the survey questionnaire).

2.1 The questionnaire

To explore social representations of Safe and Sustainable by Design, we designed an anonymous questionnaire (provided in Annex) divided into two parts: free associations (open questions), and levels of agreement or disagreement with given topical statements (closed questions). Also, some demographic data were collected about the discipline, sector, and other characteristics of respondents and their knowledge (mix of open and closed questions). The survey was estimated by the Qualtrics application to require approximately 8 minutes to complete, an estimate confirmed by a first round of tests by colleagues.

The “welcome” screen said:

The SAbyNA Project is looking at how different communities think of Safety and Sustainability by Design (SSbD), and how these views influence each other and evolve.

(...)

This questionnaire is not techno-centered; instead it focuses on social perceptions⁶.

2.1.1 Free associations

The first, open question asked participants to list the first words or ideas that came to their mind when they hear the term "**Safe by Design**". The questionnaire provided open fields for at least 2, and up to 4, responses per person.

The second screen repeated the same open question regarding the term "**Sustainability**", again prompting to enter at least 2 and up to 4 free responses.

We deliberately chose to start the consultation with free associations to capture participants' spontaneous, unfiltered orientations. These top-of-mind ideas provide a basis for understanding the different beliefs, concepts and understandings that form the specialist social representation of *Safe by Design* and *Sustainability* at this time.

⁶ Because the term “social representations” is not common parlance, our communication at times referred also to the more familiar “perceptions”.

The two prompts were presented separately in order to:

1. Reproduce exactly our 2021 pilot mini-survey question on *Safe by Design*, and thereby potentially observe any evolutions in the intervening 2 years.
2. Capture predominating representations of *Sustainability*, as a relatively new requirement which is simultaneously a well-established, multi-dimensional concept broadly used outside the SSbD field.

2.1.2 Topical statements (Agree/Disagree)

The second part of the questionnaire used closed questions. It sought to identify consensus and dissensus on common or controversial, high-level themes and concerns. This took the form of presenting topical statements about SSbD and asking participants to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement.

During the survey design stage, we generated a preliminary set of more than 3 dozen topical statements. These were derived from open-ended interviews conducted with 14 nano community members during our first phase of research (2020-21; focused at that time on SbD; see Hardy & Mays, 2022). We furthermore took into account SSbD themes debated at European project meetings, conferences and training events, or discussed in the dedicated [working group of the NanoSafety Cluster](#). We targeted a smaller set of items for a survey lasting 8 minutes in total, to maximize the chances that busy professionals would complete the entire questionnaire.

To obtain feedback from SAbyNA research scientist and industry colleagues on these topical statements, we held two online meetings in March 2023. Each gathered 8 SAbyNA volunteers representing the range of project activities. They tested the draft online survey, contributed ideas, helped to refine wording, and prioritized the statements for inclusion. The final cut included 22 items roughly divided into thematic blocs: Familiarity; Novelty; Usefulness; Engagement; Cost; and Barriers. The names of these blocs did not appear in the questionnaire. The 22 questionnaire items assigned to these blocs are presented in Table I.

Table I. Statements about SSbD organized by thematic bloc chosen at survey design stage. (*Item reversed for analysis.)

Bloc	Statements
Familiarity	I am quite familiar with current SSbD concepts.
	I have an overall understanding of how SSbD at my level impacts other parts of the value chain.
	I would like a decision support tool to help implement SSbD.
Novelty	I know who to turn to in my work environment to discuss SSbD approaches.
	SSbD induces a new mentality.
	SSbD is revolutionary.
Utility	SSbD is very different from current safety approaches.
	* SSbD requirements will not hinder innovation. ⁷
	The application of SSbD will make a positive impact on worker safety/occupational health.
Engagement	The application of SSbD will make a positive impact on the health of the environment/environmental health.
	SSbD will make it harder for industry to meet economic objectives.
	Community events are a major resource for understanding and developing SSbD.

⁷ This item is reversed for our presentation of results, i.e., in the questionnaire it was worded “SSbD requirements will hinder innovation”.

	My workplace is interested in implementing SSbD with or without external requirements to do so.
	I am personally all in favor of SSbD.
	The organizations promoting or developing SSbD don't understand my needs.
Costs	SSbD will add undue costs.
	If we don't pay the costs of implementing SSbD today, we will pay for shortcomings in the future.
	SSbD will require lots of changes in industrial processes.
	I need SSbD costs to be more quantified before I judge the approach.
Barriers	There may be industrial sectors whose processes are incompatible with an SSbD strategy.
	It will be difficult to apply SSbD without diminishing functionality and/or performance.
	Current technology has enough predictive power to enable SSbD strategy.

In the final survey instrument, after finishing free associations, participants were asked “*Are you aware of/knowledgeable about SSbD resources and/or guidance tools?*”. Those replying “yes” then saw an open field where they could indicate examples. Subsequently participants were presented with the 22 items. The survey instrument introduced each bloc by the question “*How much do you agree with these statements about Safe and Sustainable by Design?*”. The related items were presented in randomized order within blocs. Respondents were asked to rate their alignment with each statement about SSbD using a 6-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree (or, instead, to indicate “I don't know/No opinion” or “Not applicable to my situation”). At the end of this section an optional open-ended question allowed participants to propose any other statement they felt should have been included in the survey, or to provide other comments or feedback.

2.1.3 Demography

At the end of the anonymous questionnaire, we included a demographic section to gather information on participants' individual profiles, such as academic background, gender, country, sector of professional practice, domains of involvement in nanotechnology activities, and participation in government-funded nanosafety projects. Such contextual elements potentially lend insight into how participants' perceptions, attitudes and understandings are influenced by their educational background and professional context.

2.2 The co-constructive workshops

Workshops were an important part of our approach, to share methods and interim findings, to trigger discussion, and to adjust interpretations using community insights.

Four workshops were conducted in the context of larger conference or training events:

- “*Drilling into the perspectives of interdisciplinarity: Does it matter?*” (NanoSafety Training School; Venice, Italy - May 2023; plenary session).
- “*SSbD: A socially responsible approach to nanomaterials?*” (NanoSAFE '23 conference; Grenoble, France, June 2023; optional break-out session).
- “*SSbD as a cultural fact*” (SAbYNA 42-month consortium meeting; Grenoble, France, October 2023; plenary session).

- “The BOOTCAMP as a reflexive venue” (JRC/PARC SSbD Bootcamp; Ispra, Italy, October 2023; closing plenary session, conducted online with participants assembled in the face-to-face training event).

Each workshop assembled 20-30 participants representing diverse parts of the SSbD community. The first two workshops took during the period when the survey was still receiving responses; participants were requested to complete the survey before attending. Figure 1 shows an example of graphics accompanying such a request.

Figure 1. Social media image inviting survey participation before the Venice NanoSafety Training School.

Workshop design was guided by the overarching theme of the host event. Additionally, we took cues from the ongoing dialogues within the nano community, identifying emerging challenges and key ideas from prior SSbD forums. Participants engaged with the social representations methodology and results through interactive fun quizzes and hands-on group discussion sessions. Community members embraced these tasks with ease and enthusiasm, increasing their own connection around these contents, and opening up new opportunities for reflection.

2.3 Recruiting respondents

The link to invite participation in the online survey was disseminated through a targeted strategy. Over a four-month period between March and June 2023, more than one hundred personalized invitation emails were sent to identified members as well as to heads of networks of the nano community, most in Europe and some abroad, and including the OECD international Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials. The email messages invited individual participation and also requested the favor of circulating the link to colleagues or networks who could be interested.

Communication support was provided by SAbYNA and other EC-funded projects in the clusters NMBP-13 (Risk Governance), -15 and -16 (SSbD), who kindly circulated our images (Figure 2) through their newsletters and internal project listings, social media and conference announcements. We purposefully mentioned a range of areas (“advanced materials, chemicals;

plastics; innovation; all stakeholder roles”) in the final editions of several social media cards as shown in Figure 2, to remain inclusive of the populations recruited by partnership events such as the Venice NanoSafety Training School (May 2023).

Figure 2. Social media images inviting survey participation by the global community.

3. Results and Discussion

While this deliverable section reports topline results, explanation of our qualitative analytic choices leads us also to provide some interpretative discussion. The latter is clearly identified.

3.1 Obtained sample

287 questionnaire responses were started, of which only 203 were completed. (We speculate that in some cases persons may have restarted their unfinished questionnaire on a different device, and in other cases may have abandoned if they found that replying took longer than the expected 8 minutes or so.)

A total of 172 questionnaires was retained for analysis, after removal of respondents who admitted little or no familiarity with the SSbD concept (or replied “not applicable” or “no opinion”). Because respondents were self-selected in a non-systematic, non-randomized sampling strategy, we decline to speculate on the degree to which SSbD is effectively familiar to the full population coming into contact with the nanotechnology and advanced materials communication channels we employed.

Some context may be provided regarding sample size. Expert surveys in the past have typically borne on *risk and benefit perceptions*, accompanied by some governance questions. Among the largest published surveys that can be cited is Corley et al. (2009) who surveyed 363 nanoscientists and engineers in the USA. Larsson et al. (2019) surveyed 237 Swedish experts working in nanotechnology and regulation. Bertoldo et al. (2016) surveyed 39+163 experts and stakeholders in Europe (respectively, in a pilot study and a final survey).

The focus on *Safe by Design* or on *Safe and Sustainable by Design* (rather than on risk and benefit) is a new one in the survey literature. Our SAbyNA pilot study (Hardy & Mays 2022) queried 161 experts and stakeholders on Safe by Design. Publications that are more (or less) specifically related to the emergent study object of *SSbD* are few, and have typically engaged smaller numbers. Malsch et al. (2017) obtained structured data regarding decision systems for “safe and sustainable development of nano-enabled products” from 13+36 stakeholders (respectively, in a pre-study and final survey), while the Furxhi et al. (2022) survey of current challenges for *SSbD* was completed by approximately 24 European project leaders and other major stakeholders (actual N unreported). The present SAbyNA survey of N=172 appears to be the largest to date focused specifically on *SSbD*.

3.2 Demographics

We report here the topline frequencies obtained on the demographic aspects surveyed. At the present stage of analysis, these independent variables do not appear to discriminate other responses to a significant degree.

3.2.1 Geographic location

The 172 questionnaires retained for processing gathered the views of people working in a total of 31 countries. Figure 3 shows the location of respondents in EU Member States (69%) or in other world regions. The great majority of our participants stated they work in geographic Europe, representing 81% overall.

Figure 3. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by region in which they work.

3.2.2 Sector of activity

Figure 4 shows the distribution of self-declared professional sector. The most represented are Academia, and Research & Technological Organizations (RTO). Because of a very small number of respondents from the Policy sector (N=5), we merged Policy and Regulation. This combined category remains the smallest portion of our sample.

Figure 4. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by professional sector.

3.2.3 Primary disciplinary field of training

Regarding the "Primary disciplinary field of training", we let the participants answer freely and then grouped their answers into four distinct categories for our analysis:

- a) *Physical sciences and engineering* - Includes focus on chemistry, materials, computing and math as well as biotechnology.
- b) *Life sciences* - Includes focus on living systems at cellular or individual level.
- c) *Environmental sciences* - Includes focus on living and/or nonliving systems at ecological level.
- d) *Social sciences and humanities* - Includes focus on society and individuals, as well as law, management and administration.

Figure 5 shows the percent distribution of respondents by primary discipline of training, with the majority classified in physical sciences, and the remaining categories more evenly distributed.

Figure 5. Percent distribution of participants (N=172) by primary discipline.

We expect to re-code the disciplinary information for further analysis, perhaps with reference to the categorization suggested by Powell (2008) and characterized by Johansson and Boholm (2017): "upstream" and "downstream" nanoscience disciplines or practices. We shall also assess whether this standpoint has changed among any of the 28% of respondents who indicate that in their current field of work they exercise a discipline differing from their primary training.

3.2.4 Involvement in a government sponsored-project

61% of participants acknowledged their past or current involvement in government-sponsored projects on nanosafety, while 39% answered negatively.

This feature of demography will be examined in future analyses to be reported in a peer-reviewed article.

3.3 Free associations

3.3.1 Data coding categories and frequencies

For the free associations to "Safe by Design" and "Sustainability", we undertook a careful reading and categorization of the "top of mind" words, ideas and concepts provided by the participants. This qualitative analysis was conducted using Atlas.ti 23 software by two researchers, hand coding according to a "grounded theory" (Glaser and Strauss 1967; Malsch et al. 2015) or bottom-up approach. The first round of coding yielded 15 and 12 differentiated categories for *Safe by Design* and *Sustainable* respectively. A smaller set was sought in order to clarify later semi-quantitative and factor analyses. Four iterative rounds of coding, discussion and harmonization, as well as preliminary factor analyses, yielded for each of the two questions a reduced final total of 7 distinct category labels. While sometimes conceptually overlapping (certain ideas could potentially be placed in more than one category), the categories were kept cohesive by a rigorous final set of coding rules. These categories are posited as overarching cognitive frames used by participants in their spontaneous responses to the prompts.

3.3.2 "Safe by Design"

The opening question asked: *What are the first words or ideas that come to your mind when you hear the term "Safe by Design"?* We gathered 537 words or ideas associated with "Safe by Design", which we categorized into the 7 groups (see Box 4) displayed by descending order of frequency in Figure 6.

Box 4. "Safe by Design" Free Associations Codebook (labels and category contents)

Anticipation and Risk Control: The ideas in this group refer explicitly to a planning approach, with actions aimed at identifying, preventing or avoiding hazard, risk or adverse consequences, reflecting a systematic, strategic and proactive deployment of knowledge for risk management. It includes concepts such as "Prevention"; "Bigger picture"; "Proactive"; "Toxicity"; "Exposure"; "Intelligent design"; or "Optimization".

One Health: The focus is here on terms related to safety, concepts such as human or occupational health and safety, and environmental or ecological health and safety. Taken all together, responses assigned to this category underscore the intrinsic interconnectedness between human, non-human and ecological health, safety and well-being. This influenced our choice of the label One Health, a unified and transdisciplinary approach which has lately been cited in the nano domain (Saarimäki et al. 2023), and which emphasizes the need for integrative and holistic management to ensure a sustainable and healthy balance across these targets. The category contains concepts like "Planet care"; "Work safety"; "Health"; "Eco-friendliness"; or "Water".

Materials and Processes: Here are grouped the ideas revolving around material components and structure of particles, as well as manufacturing activities and processes. It encompasses all aspects of materiality without specific judgment, like the simple mention of "Technology", "Nanotechnology" and "New technology", but also materiality accompanied by judgment, such as "Best technology". It also includes mentions of "Design" or the design process without a strategic element indicating its integration in an anticipatory approach. Terms include "Structure"; "Materials safety"; or "Chemistry".

Socio-Economic World: This category takes up the intricate interplay between nano-enabled products and industry, economic factors, societal considerations, ethical responsibilities, regulatory frameworks, and end users' needs or experience. It includes terms such as "Less costs"; "Responsibility"; "Quality of the product"; or "Economy". It also comprehends projects and

organizations such as "SAByNA" or "NanoReg" and "Europe" and organized initiatives such as "Open science".

Positive Quality: This category communicates the various positive values, qualities, innovations, and overall benefits that may result from embracing SbD (excluding considerations related specifically to health and safety outcomes, classed as One Health). It also designates ongoing improvements and advances resulting from Safe by Design practices. It includes terms like "Easy to use"; "Innovative"; "Resilience"; "Trust"; "Effective"; or "Freedom". It also embraces assessments of SbD such as "Clever" or "Smart".

Circularity: The ideas grouped here are related to sustainability practices, life cycle considerations, circular economy principles, recycling, and biocompatible materials. Their presence in the data set indicates the importance, for those who voiced it, of integrating environmentally conscious and sustainable practices into the SbD approach. The category contains terms such as "Sustainability"; "LCA", "Longer life span"; "Degradation"; "Design of the end-of-life"; "Reusable"; or "Circular".

Skepticism: This last category captures some reservations towards Safe by Design, including obstacles, challenges, uncertainties, as well as outright rejection of the concept. This group serves as an opportunity to look at and to explore the doubts, concerns, or critiques people may have regarding the implementation and acceptance of Safe by Design. Among the terms are "Challenging"; "It is a crazy concept"; "Buzz word"; "Should not block open innovation"; "Slowing down"; and "Safe for what/whom?".

Figure 6. Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term "Safe by Design" (N_{associations}=537, from 172 participants)

Based on these overall frequencies, we may observe that:

- Respondents represent "Safe by Design" (SbD) above all as a preventive, proactive and strategic approach.
- SbD inspires thoughts of a broad range of interconnected health and safety benefits.
- The representation is furthermore composed simultaneously of concrete and abstract aspects, that is to say at the level of both materials and processes, and socio-economic issues and impacts.
- Less marked here is any degree of immediate association between "Safe by Design" and sustainability or life-cycle considerations.
- The SbD concept has inspired positive evaluations or observations in several instances, while it appears challenging or controversial to a minority of respondents.

3.3.3 “Sustainability”

The second question of the survey asked *What are the first words or ideas that come to your mind when you hear the term “Sustainability”?*

We chose to ask for free associations to “Sustainability” (and not “Sustainable by Design”) in order to learn the specific meanings attributed by our study population to this generally used term. Importantly, the terms “sustainable” and “sustainability” (unlike “Safety by Design” or other specialist terms) entered popular discourse many years ago. Their broad social representation, stimulated in recent years by the mindful elevation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, may have a large number of meanings, connected or not to the chemicals realm. “Sustainability” is also an operationalized term in many domains, widely known to rest on three pillars (environmental, economic, social).

In the period of designing the SAbYNA questionnaire (first trimester of 2023), we observed that the nano community present in several European and project meetings discussed sustainability with a predominantly environmental focus⁸. The free associations task is suitable to identify which meanings emerge spontaneously in our context, and to check the proportion of different meanings.

This free association task collected 549 separate words or ideas on the concept, which could be divided by researchers into 7 categories (Box 5). Four categories (again found by a grounded theory approach, discussed by the two coders and harmonized in several rounds) could be labeled similarly to those found in the preceding (“Safe by Design”) coding exercise. However, 3 sets of ideas highlighting specific differentiated features of sustainability called for distinct treatment: *Eco-friendly*, *Carbon Footprint*⁹, and *Future*. Figure 7 displays the resulting groupings by descending order of frequency.

Box 5. “Sustainability” Free Associations Codebook (labels and category contents)

Circularity: The ideas in this category communicate a circular paradigm that purposefully considers the entire life cycle of products, achieving balance in systems. The holistic perspective here recognizes interdependence of environmental, social, and economic dimensions. Quotes include “Life-cycle”; “Living in balance”; “Recycling”; “Purpose”; “3 dimensions”; and “Financial or environmental options”.

Eco-friendly: This category gives explicit expression to green objectives and qualities. It encompasses notions of bio preservation, ecological awareness, and non-toxicity, and all the words used to evoke and describe nature. It integrates relationships and actions directed specifically towards environmental protection. It contains terms such as “Biodegradable”; “Environment-friendly”; “Plant”; “Use of biological materials”; and “Biomimicry”.

⁸ For instance, this was our personal observation at the “Future-proof Approaches for Risk Governance” conference organized 24-25 January 2023 at the OECD (Paris, France) by the EC-funded NMBP-13 projects NANORIGO, Gov4Nano and RiskGONE.

⁹ An internal reviewer (A.C.) observed: ‘I would like to stress the importance of specific definitions (where they exist) of terms used (e.g. as categories) in the report such as “carbon footprint” – the **total** amount of greenhouse gases (such as CO₂ and CH₄) added to (or taken away from) the atmosphere during the lifecycle. This is a complex and time consuming and hence costly calculation which might benefit from quality assured on line tools.’ The SAbYNA RRI team wishes to clarify that indeed, the category name “Carbon Footprint” used for our content analysis/coding is qualitative and is not intended to suggest that all free associations that could be grouped under this category corresponded to a precise, quantitative vision of anthropogenic footprint. See Box 5.

Carbon Footprint: This category addresses anthropogenic impact on the environment. It designates ideas centered on the production and use of natural resources and energy, and the management of resulting waste products such as CO₂ emissions. This category includes “Waste”; “Contamination”; “Use of less materials”; “Prevent emissions”; “Clean energy”; and “Ethical use of resources”.

Socio-Economic World: Similar to the category used for Safe by Design, this grouping encapsulates concepts of production, regulation, responsibility, development, ethics & social aspects, from healthcare to the financial market. This category represents the societal and economic pillars of sustainability, and reflects participants' recognition of the necessity of sustainable development for the global community. It includes terms such as “Society”; “Responsible”; “Profit”; “Degrowth”; “Fundamental to business”; and “Human rights”.

Future: This grouping portrays a forward-looking perspective, where *Sustainability* invokes the long term and durability. It gathers mentions of long-term vision or long-lasting materials, as well as processes that engage the future such as “Climate change”. It also includes contemplations about the future, some of them tinged by eco-anxiety: awareness of and concern about upcoming environmental challenges, expressing emotional and evaluative elements. This group contains ideas such as “Long term”; “Long life”; “Protect the future”; “Next generation”; and “Urgent”.

Positive Quality: This category brings together optimistic observations, hopes and aspirations towards positive change and the well-being of the planet. It links sustainability with confidence and resourcefulness. It names action features to foster positive sustainable outcomes, like “Data transparency” and “Safe production”. Terms also include: “Essential”; “Victory”; “Trust and confidence”; and “Better”.

Skepticism: This category groups expressions of a lack of confidence in the power or seriousness of the sustainability concept, and even rejection. It captures doubt, reservations, and a critical perspective, including terms like: “Hype”; “Buzzword”; “Very very difficult to achieve”; “Often false flag”; “Is sustainable equal to safe?”; and “Should not hinder innovation”.

Figure 7. Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term “Sustainability” (N_{associations} =549, from 172 participants)

Based on these overall frequencies, we may observe that:

- The basic *Circular* systems paradigm emerges as the strongest feature in the representation of “Sustainability”.

- The presence of other relatively strong, distinguishable categories *Eco-friendly*, *Carbon Footprint*, and *Socio-Economic World* suggests that the representation of “Sustainability” is both complex and highly operationalized.
- A *Future-oriented* consciousness, including aspects of eco-anxiety, demanded a distinct category to highlight this cognitive and emotional dimension of the “Sustainability” representation.
- The representation includes some strongly *Positive* elements, as well as an equal proportion of *Skepticism* (doubts and critiques) addressed to the concept of “Sustainability”.

Of note, if *Eco-friendly* and *Carbon Footprint* categories are combined, then the environmental pillar of sustainability, as expected, emerges as the strongest component in the social representation conveyed by our population.

3.3.4 Mapping predominant relations between associations – at two periods

In this section we display a particular analysis that maps relationships between different ideas or notions invoked by respondents in their free associations. We also incorporate data allowing insight into the evolution of social representations of “Safe by Design” over a two-year period.

We conducted identical analysis on the free associations to “Safe by Design” collected at two different times: in the first quarter of 2021 and in the second quarter of 2023¹⁰. It may well be that certain individuals provided data at both times; this was not investigated by a direct question in 2023. We believe that because we are studying collective representations in a time of rapid cultural evolution, our qualitative analysis is not invalidated by the eventuality of overlapping samples.

In order to perform a comparison, we re-coded our 2021 data (Hardy & Mays 2022), this time using the 7 categories developed for the 2023 “Safe by Design” free associations data (cf. the code book, Box 4 in section 3.3.2 above). The rounded percent frequency of categories evoked in 2021 (Fig. 8) is generally comparable to that found in 2023 (see Fig. 6). The largest changes seen in the course of two years are: *Anticipation & Control* dips three points (from 31% to 28%) and *Positive Qualities* grow 3 points (from 9% to 12%).

¹⁰ The expert samples may reasonably be assumed to be generally comparable, recruited through similar channels, in 2021 relying e.g. on an announcement during an NMBP-15 SBYDOMA project webinar. This “Legal Workshop on Safe by Design” (28 January 2021) solicited stakeholders from diverse global regions, including: “scientists, industry and commercial managers, public policy stakeholders, lawyers (...), trade associations, NGOs and all other stakeholders having an interest in the safe design of (nano)technologies.”

Figure 8. 2021- Rounded percent distribution into categories of free associations to the term “Safe by Design” (N_{associations}= 456, from 164 participants in Hardy & Mays 2022)

Beyond simple frequencies, it is possible to examine the binary linkages between categories observable in each dataset. Investigating top of mind categories that are typically paired by respondents yields a more complex view of the emergent representation, and can thereby help identify any changes from time 1 to time 2 that may be masked by similar rounded frequencies. We therefore tabulated the co-occurrence of any two categories in each individual’s line of data. Resulting relationship maps are shown and interpreted below.

Figure 9 displays the respective years’ top linked categories, using an arbitrary cut-off of 15% of total observed linkages. (Subsidiary below-threshold linkages between principal categories in 2023 are displayed for information.) In this analysis, unlike the basic frequencies, highly suggestive differences are found in results of the two consultations separated by two years.

Figure 9. Linkages observed between categories of free associations to the term “Safe by Design” in 2021 (from 164 respondents) and in 2023 (from 172 respondents). The N stated in each disc represents the number of surveyed individuals who mentioned this category at least one time (multiple mentions by one person are not counted in this analysis). Thickness of connector varies with percent of all observed binary linkages (frequency of linkage is also noted).

The comparison of maps suggests that the representation of “Safe by Design” has benefitted in two years from greater elaboration and some consolidation:

- In the earlier data set, the average number of ideas or notions returned by each respondent was 2.78. This average rises to 3.12 two years later.
- In 2021, three linkages surpassed the arbitrary cut-off. In 2023, three principal linkages are again seen, but with higher percent rates than those seen earlier, and engaging an enlarged set of categories (4 rather than 3).
- *Anticipation & Risk Control* is at the center of this new set of relationships. In 2023, while less frequently cited in overall percent share (compare Safe by Design histograms, Figs. 6 & 8), it is nonetheless more tightly linked to a broader range of categories. Subsidiary linkages between the latter do not surpass threshold. This dynamic suggests that *Anticipation & Risk Control* plays a more structuring role in 2023 representations.
- Importantly, in 2023 the category *Socio-Economic World* enters the linked landscape. At a 17% rate of linkage, this category makes a showing equal to the profiles observed in 2021.
- The tradeoff resides in part in the linkage between *One Health* and *Materials & Processes*, which plunges by about 1/3 even while *Materials & Processes* is more frequently voiced in 2023 (compare histograms).

Anticipation & Risk Control predominates in both years as a central defining idea behind “Safe by Design”. Total mentions in free association place this category at the head of histograms (Figs. 6 & 8). A similar 58% and 59% of all individual respondents in 2021 and 2023 respectively evoked this category at least once while simultaneously linking it with one or more other notions.

However, 2023’s strengthened and diversified linkages centering on *Anticipation & Risk Control* highlight the growing significance of “Safe by Design” as a strategic, holistic and pro-active vision, integrated into a broad variety of areas and levels of concern. In this map of relationships, SbD appears to shift from a focus on the management of materials for health (strongest linkage in 2021), towards a preventive and operational risk control approach conceived in 2023 as a driving force in achieving *One Health* outcomes. The strongest linkage in 2023, between *Materials & Processes* and anticipatory design, suggests that this upstream relationship is becoming more explicit and better understood. *Socio-economic* themes – whether concerning industry or larger societal stakes – also move dramatically into view as relevant to the anticipatory stance.

With appropriate reserves given the modest numbers, these observations may nonetheless reflect a maturing of perspectives and a growing awareness in the field of Safe by Design and its applicability. The described evolution in ways of relating ideas could be the result of a collective construction of meaning over time, where participants have broadened and deepened their understanding of the SbD concept, elaborated its implications, and exchanged more and more with each other on these subjects. If true, this denotes a typical cultural process of building social representations: more people share a more elaborated idea.

Regarding free associations to “Sustainability”, data are available only for 2023. Figure 10 displays the linkages found among categories, again using an arbitrary cut-off of 15% of all observed linkages (and displaying for information an under-threshold subsidiary linkage).

Figure 10. Linkages observed between categories of free associations to the term “Sustainability” in 2023 (from 172 respondents). N in each disc = surveyed individuals mentioning category at least one time. Thickness of connector varies with % of all observed binary linkages (frequency of linkage is also noted).

For “Sustainability”, we observe four categories benefiting from five notable linked relationships. As mentioned above in 3.3.3, the categories *Eco-friendly* and *Carbon Footprint* taken together achieve an overall frequency of mentions (21% + 18%; Fig. 5) indicating that the environmental pillar is most salient to our population. The fact that their own linkage (that is, frequency of simultaneous mention by any individual) of 16% is not particularly strong reinforces the coders’ impression that these two frames are differentiated by individuals. They highlight the distinction between an ecological and natural-world sensibility (*Eco-friendly*) versus a focus on anthropogenic impacts largely centered on energy resource use (*Carbon Footprint*). The map suggests that these domains of concern play distinct roles in the representation, through their outstandingly strong linkage with the notion of *Circularity* (26% and, 24% respectively). The emergent social representation of “Sustainability” appears to revolve on the possibility to preserve healthy ecosystems, and also to reduce footprint, by using the circular paradigm and strategy.

Socio-economic World achieves a comfortable linkage with *Eco-friendly* but lesser linkages with other categories. There are few direct hints in the data as to why our sample pairs the social and economic pillars most frequently with the eco-sensibility frame. This specific pairing in today’s top-of-mind thoughts may reflect what SAbyNA workshop participants identified as “stereotypes” or “key words”, i.e. an existing three-pillar social representation of *Sustainability*.

At conferences and in publications¹¹, SSbD developers today voice that the socio-economic domain remains insufficiently operationalized. As some survey respondents also took care to state (see section 3.4.4 and footnote 13), *“The socio-economic development of SSbD needs attention;”* *“Current development of the socio-economic side of SSbD may not be sufficient to facilitate its implementation”*. If the free association task can be repeated in future surveys, perhaps we may see evolutions that shed light on today’s starting position.

¹¹ Communications in 2022 and 2023 by the EC and the JRC surrounding the JRC SSbD Framework have explicitly acknowledged that to date, development focused on the environment pillar, with less attention to socio-economic dimensions (cf. e.g. paragraph 13, p3 of the Commission Recommendation of 2022).

3.4 Topical aspects of Safe and Sustainable by Design

Our survey of SSbD social representations in the nano community addressed a variety of topical areas, designated at our survey design stage as follows: Familiarity, Novelty, Usefulness, Engagement, Costs, and Barriers. These thematic blocs do not appear to be strictly borne out by the obtained results (a principal components analysis, not reported in this deliverable, indicated that other groupings may better characterize the data).

We report here the topline results on these topical statements, organized in terms of consensus (supermajority of like answers, defined at $\geq 60\%$ accord), dispersion or dissensus (no clear tendency), or absence of judgment (predominance of “don’t know/no opinion” or “not applicable”). We note particular areas where meaning could be further explored by future stakeholder interviews, or by refined survey items.

In this section we also report additional survey items or other ideas entered by respondents in a specific open field of the questionnaire.

3.4.1 Consensus items – Supermajority agreement

Twelve of our 22 statements gather consensus, which we have defined as enjoying a 3/5 supermajority (60%) of agreement. The top half of this set – the six items at the top of Fig. 11 – reach or surpass 80% agreement. Moreover, five of those six strong consensus items are led by the response option “strongly agree”. The set of six standout statements should be considered by this simple measure to be important features of the social representation of SSbD today.

Figure 11. Consensus statements enjoying a supermajority ($\geq 60\%$) of agreement. Ordered by rounded % of overall agreement in descending order. (*Item reversed for analysis.)

These top six standout consensus statements portray strong support for SSbD within the consulted nano community, highlighting its safety and health benefits and its transformative potential. They highlight the imperative need to adopt the strategy, as well as personal commitment to the SSbD approach and demand for resources facilitating its application.

The top statement of consensus is that “*application of SSbD will make a positive impact on the health of the environment/environmental health*”.

- This highlights very strong community confidence that SSbD is a beneficial and effective approach to protect the biosphere.

A sense of urgency and determination are communicated in the neighboring items:

- In “*If we don't pay the costs of implementing SSbD today, we will pay for shortcomings in the future,*” the word “costs” may be interpreted in broad terms: rethinking, redesigning, retooling, and associated financial investment.
- “*I am personally all in favor of SSbD*” heralds a feeling of fit between needs and action. This strong endorsement is social capital for the SSbD community, simultaneously reflecting and reinforcing ongoing commitment to operationalizing SSbD.

A positive impact from SSbD to be expected for “*worker safety and occupational health*” is also a standout, although the “strongly agree” response option loses 10 points while more moderate agreement rises.

- Does this somewhat less unitary (if dominant) expectation for workers to reap a positive impact reflect belief that a) workers’ benefit will not be the most significant contribution by SSbD, or b) the occupational setting is already characterized by a very high level of protection, or c) the impact of SSbD on working environments is seen to have more unknowns attached than the overall impact of the principle? These questions could be explored by interviews or a future survey.

The standout endorsement of “*SSbD induces a new mentality*” suggests a shared consciousness of the cognitive and behavioral implications of the needed paradigm shift¹² emphasized by framework developers.

- This consensus may be indicative of a general receptiveness to the adoption of new perspectives and ways of thinking associated with SSbD.

The next supermajority consensus statements are not led by “strongly agree”, but reveal more varied degrees of assent. Their profile is nonetheless clearly defined by low rates of disagreement. These elements of today’s SSbD social representation are interesting signs of an enthusiastic dynamic of development.

- There appears to be general confidence that “*SSbD will not hinder innovation*”.
- A super majority believes that developing SSbD is a collaborative activity calling for transdisciplinary dialogue in “*community events*”; while some proportion state they

¹² Cf. the statement heard at the CSS High-level Roundtable; see Section 4.2 and footnote 15 of this report. Elsewhere, mindset shift is seen as a condition of stabilizing innovative technologies (Kertcher & Coslor, 2018, p. 77). Lacy et al. (2010) observed mindset shift in the massive integration of three-pillar sustainability into business practices by UN Global Compact CEOs over a three-year period.

don't know or have no opinion, no respondent says this is "not applicable" to their context.

- The consensus includes a feeling of being generally "*familiar with current SSbD concepts*", which may translate a shared sense of cultural integration.
- For most, including an increased proportion of "strongly agree", SSbD dialogue partners are quite near to hand and visible in the "*work environment*."

However, the final consensus items may challenge the dynamic of confidence, given that "strongly agree" has dropped ten points.

- A supermajority agrees that "*SSbD will require lots of changes to industrial processes*", but the proportion of those only "somewhat" agreeing, or professing ignorance, has risen.
- Many comfortably agree they have an "*overall understanding of how SSbD at [their] level impacts other parts of the value chain*", but the rate of disagreement as well as a feeling of not being involved ("not applicable") rise slightly.

These bottom two items of consensus might be particularly good statements to bring into community discussion, to check SSbD's real impacts on "*industrial processes*", and to reinforce the useful understanding of how stakeholders contribute across the circular dynamic of SSbD.

3.4.2 Dispersion/ dissensus, or ambiguous responses

Looking at items without a supermajority, defined as 60% accord, we can identify two types of lack of consensus. These are a) statements marked by swing opinions, and b) statements marked by dissensus or dispersion in replies. Eight of our 22 items can be viewed in this light.

We call "somewhat agree" and "somewhat disagree" swing opinions, in the hypothesis that if something changed even slightly in the SSbD context, these respondents could change their assessment. When "somewhat" is infrequently chosen, the weight of opinion can potentially cluster on firmer options. However, if the sum of swing responses surpasses 40%, this ambiguity prevents any attainment elsewhere of a 60% supermajority. For three statements, the sum of swing opinions indeed settled these items into an ambiguous space (Table II):

Table II. Statements dominated by swing opinions ("somewhat agree" or "somewhat disagree"). Rounded percentages of response.

Rounded sum of "somewhat"	Statement
49%	Current technology has enough predictive power to enable SSbD strategy.
48%	It will be difficult to apply SSbD without diminishing functionality and/or performance.
48%	SSbD will make it harder for industry to meet economic objectives.

Opinions expressed on five other statements are highly dispersed. For these items, no supermajority nor even simple majority is achieved by any response modality. Here the absence of a clear "agree" or "disagree" valence is not due to a large number of swing opinions ("somewhat"). Nor is it due to a predominance of "don't know/no opinion" or "not applicable" replies. Table III presents these dissensus statements, with an interpretative category suggested in the first column.

Table III. Dissensus statements.

Interpretative category	Statement
<i>Dissensus on SSbD's novelty</i>	SSbD is very different from current safety approaches.
	SSbD is revolutionary.
<i>Dissensus on how SSbD can be applied at production level</i>	SSbD will add undue costs.
	I need SSbD costs to be more quantified before I judge the approach.
	There may be industrial sectors whose processes are incompatible with an SSbD strategy.

Two of these items translate dissensus as to the novelty of SSbD.

- We suggest that widely varying visions on “what’s new, what’s the same,” by stakeholders respectively proposing or applying SSbD strategies, may have implications for operationalization or ease of application.

Three statements, intriguingly, translate doubts or at least divergent visions regarding how SSbD can be applied at production level, and in particular how well its potential costs are known. The absence of a clear tendency, and the highly mixed responses, reveal the perceived complexity of applying SSbD in all industrial sectors.

- We suggest that, like the statement “*SSbD will require lots of changes in industrial processes*” situated at the bottom of clear consensus items, these three dissensus topics should be discussed across sectors in the next period of SSbD development. Expressing and explaining points of view as to costs and compatibility could pinpoint areas where agreement actually exists, areas where tools and guidance are available, and areas where further clarification should be a common priority.

3.4.3 Not applicable or no judgment formed

For the remaining two statements out of 22, the sum of “not applicable” and “don’t know/no opinion” responses prevent a supermajority from forming elsewhere. In both cases, “not applicable” is the predominant response. Table IV shows the statements on which a judgment is not formed by the consulted community at this time.

Table IV. Statements on which no judgment is formed.

Rounded sum of “NA” or “DK/ NO”	Statement
47%	The organizations promoting or developing SSbD don't understand my needs.
43%	My workplace is interested in implementing SSbD with or without external requirements to do so.

Future analysis can check which subpopulations communicate this sense of slight disconnection from the actual SSbD implementation dynamic.

3.4.4 “What did we miss?”

Our survey sought to value participants' expert reflection and their curiosity going beyond the proposed topical statements. With this in mind, we included an optional open question: “*After agreeing/disagreeing with the statements above, is there a statement we missed? Which statement would YOU add to this questionnaire?*”.

Suggestions were presented by 42 of the 172 respondents. Their open responses contained proposed additional statements for future agree/disagree assessment, and other comments and reflections (including some criticism of the survey format itself). Two responses could be split into distinct components, resulting in a final set of 44 inputs. To identify the topical areas of curiosity and concern among this subset of respondents, we coded the 44 inputs using the *Safe by Design* free association categories (Box 4). Figure 12 indicates the thematic spectrum of the full set of 44 inputs.

Figure 12. Categorization of respondents' proposed additional items or commentary (N=44, from 172 participants).

Socio-economic considerations clearly dominate the additional commentary. The two following categories (*Anticipation & Risk Control; Skepticism*) are more or less matched in volume, whereas remaining categories are less present.

We further classified the content of the seven critical or doubting remarks identified as “*Skepticism*”. Two were critical only of the survey itself. The rest were spread across other categories, with three placed by us in “*Socio-economic World*”. While no more representative than other commentary, these examples may indicate obstacles to acceptance or implementation of SSbD:

- “People working with SSbD think this is something new - the good thing is that this is not new at all, it has been around at least 15-20 years or more (but not under the SSbD name). So I don't need a tool - a tool can be a way to over-complicate things (= slow down the process of change). Typical for this type of questionnaires are that they are far too much with a inside the box thinking due to lack of experiences from industry.”
- “More thought should be given to the real world we live in and more consideration for the 90% of people who are struggling to survive. Most of the Sustainability/safe by design is a concept that the liberal elite want in their Utopian vision.”
- “It is sometimes hard to answer simplistic to these complex questions. SSbD and decisions on a development path and balance with cost needs to be considered against

the real predicted impact. It will likely cost companies more to follow a SSbD recommendation. But the overall health, societal and environmental bill should be less and the solution ethically responsible. All these elements already exist in responsible innovation strategies and responsible governance in chemicals. The challenge is to get it out and live in companies in general. A lot of nice academic developments have been made, but how much has been taken up by users afterwards? How do we get beyond the academic exercise?"

Within the 44 remarks categorized by us in Fig. 12, we identified a total of 22 succinct statements that could potentially be worded as survey items. These are presented in Table V, sometimes lightly reworded for clarity, and organized on the same free association categories. Some commentary identified by us in the first round as "skeptical" subsequently yielded other category items that are included below. We have furthermore suggested thematic groupings (column 1). An asterisk before an item indicates that it was selected¹³ for discussion at the co-constructive workshop held at NanoSAFE23 (Grenoble, June 2023).

Table V. Respondents' suggestions for additional survey items, coded on Safe by Design free association categories and grouped. (* Item discussed at NanoSAFE '23 workshop, Grenoble, June 2023.)

Category	Additional statements (slightly reworded when necessary for clarity)
Socio-Economic World	
<i>Presence</i>	SSbD is applied in my/your workplace.
<i>Effectiveness</i>	SSbD's focus on incremental improvement may not align with the radical changes needed to combat climate change and meet the EU climate goals.
	Fundamental economic principles, including the concept of growth/degrowth, must be reconsidered for genuine ecological sustainability.
	The socio-economic side of SSbD needs development.
<i>Costs</i>	* The implementation of SSbD could potentially be a barrier to EU competitiveness.
	* SSbD may create new costs that the consumer is not willing to pay.
<i>Sectors</i>	SSbD holds the potential to properly regulate industrial activity.
	A specific statement of SSbD is needed for different sectors because SSbD will have different impacts on academia and industry.
	The SSbD approach is not accepted among all the communities.
<i>Awareness</i>	* The SSbD mentality needs to be activated from the earliest stages of higher education in all scientific fields.
	There is sufficient outreach to provide awareness of the SSbD concept to the lay community.
	The SSbD community should extend dissemination beyond research/industry to the general public.
	* SSbD should enhance public involvement through comprehensible and applicable approaches for all stakeholders including the general population.

[Table V continues next page]

¹³ In fact nine statements, mainly in the category "Socio-Economic World", were selected for debate at the NanoSAFE '23 workshop. However, the four listed below (which are well-worded for potential inclusion in a future survey) do not appear in Table V because each belongs to an incomplete line of data that was removed from final analysis.

- "Current development of the socio-economic side of SSbD may not be sufficient to facilitate its implementation."
- "SSbD requires that environmental well-being and climate protection be considered on an equal footing with profit."
- "Understanding and acceptance of SSbD by companies needs to be facilitated."
- "SSbD needs a trusted safe space for international cooperation."

Of interest, workshop participants chose two of these removed statements as translating a high priority (see Table VI, section 3.5.2).

[Table V, continued]

Anticipation and Risk Control	
Tools	There is an SSbD tool/strategy available for my sector.
	A comprehensive list of SSbD tools for each of the five life cycle stages is needed.
	More emphasis is needed on developing predictive tools with extrapolation capacity.
Concepts	More traditional chemical toxicology risk evaluation expertise should be called on for SSbD.
	* The SSbD concept lacks consideration of sufficiency and non-chemical alternatives.
Circularity	
Need	SSbD is crucial for addressing future climate and energy challenges.
	Investment in SSbD is necessary to achieve better global resource and waste management in our increasingly populated world of finite resources.
Materials and Processes	
21	Safety professionals should be involved in the early stages of the design process.
22	SSbD is very useful for new nano-technology but its application to existing ones (mostly under IP) presents challenges.

The diversity of proposed items highlights the multidimensional complexity of SSbD and its operationalization. Socio-economic aspects are particularly salient among the suggestions. This may reflect the current relative maturity of exposure/hazard assessment and risk strategies, and the desire to move forward on the less mastered pillars of sustainability. Interestingly, broad societal awareness of SSbD emerges as an imperative, as does the need for greater understanding and acceptance of SSbD by businesses. Concerns remain about potential new costs perceived by consumers and the impact on EU competitiveness.

All in all, the additional comments offered by respondents portray the current challenges associated with SSbD, underlining the need to maintain a holistic and balanced approach, geared towards the inclusion of all stakeholders in the dialogue.

3.5 Co-constructive workshops: Community reflections

Four workshops were conducted during which interim data and analyses were proposed for elaboration by community members. These workshops raised awareness of the notion of social representations and of social science methods to investigate community beliefs, attitudes, and practices. They also provided an opportunity for participants to discuss the survey issues and the opinion trends revealed by the data, offering their own interpretations and deepening (shared) reflection. We consider this discussion activity to contribute to the consolidation of the SSbD cultural dynamic. Finally, several insights were expressed that could help shape the analysis of final data. In this section we share details of workshop conduct.

Of note, in two cases (Venice, Ispra) the SAbyNA RRI team was entrusted with facilitating the closing session of the training event, including participants' evaluation of their learning experience.

3.5.1 Venice NanoSafety Training School

The face-to-face NanoSafety Training School in Venice (May 2023) was dedicated to Interdisciplinarity in SSbD and allowed us to work with a new generation of professionals engaged in the SSbD landscape (approximately 17 participants face-to-face and 3-5 online), as

well as a subgroup of 5 confirmed professionals highly involved in developing the SSbD field. Our workshop responded to the school’s overall theme by asking: *“Interdisciplinarity: Does it matter?”*. The opening presentation of interim survey findings shared basic knowledge about the theory of social representations, and also used an engaging game. This sensitized participants to how semi-quantitative treatment of qualitative results may be interpreted. The Mentimeter quiz questions were (items not reproduced here):

- *Do you expect that this survey item got a consensual reply?*
- *Select the item – or items – that got massive consensual Agreement.*
- *Select the item – or items – that got a strongly split or divided result.*
- *This item got a rather consensual reply. Do you expect to find the relative consensus or majority in Agreement or in Disagreement?*
- *Looking still at the same item, we know that the majority Disagreed. What about the minority opinion: which subgroup do you expect formed this minority (=which persons Agreed to this item)?* [options included: certain disciplines; persons agreeing with a particular other item; persons who have not participated in EU-funded projects; none of the above/mixed minority]
- *Which of the following factors do you expect to be an explanation for the differences in responses?* [Sectors, Disciplines, Gender, Other?]

After this game, interim results (overall and per sector - not per discipline) on selected agree/disagree items were presented, and discussed in subgroup. As shown in Figure 13, participants were prompted both to notice and interpret (cross-sector) consensus or dissensus, and to reflect on the implications for consolidating both social representations of SSbD and community culture.

Figure 13. Discussion questions from the SAbYNA RRI workshop at Venice NanoSafety Training School (using interim survey results, May 2023)

One subgroup offered the insight that the paradoxical results indicated in Fig. 13 (right side) reflect the dynamic nature of the SSbD field. They interpreted that community members presently need to continuously adapt to new developments, even while recognizing familiar components of knowledge and practice activated by the SSbD paradigm.

Participants were invited to form subgroups to discuss their understanding of “interdisciplinarity,” where and how they experience it, and to report back to plenary. Overall, the attendees emphasized their surprise when encountering the diversity of disciplines involved in SSbD, and their growing awareness of a real interdisciplinarity. In particular, they expressed their new grasp of SSbD as including social studies and social factors, broadening their

understanding of the field and underlining the importance of this perspective in future SSbD initiatives.

3.5.2 NanoSAFE '23 Conference

NanoSAFE '23 was the 8th International Conference on Health and Safety Issues Related to a Socially Responsible Approach to Nanomaterials (Grenoble, June 2023). Our two-part workshop was an initiation to a social sciences approach and some theory, for a total of 20 attendees representing the full range of surveyed sectors. We invited participants to explore interim free association results and try their hand at content analysis by generating categories. We then shared some of the additional SSbD topical statements collected from questionnaire respondents (see starred items in Table V; also see footnote 13) and invited subgroups to prioritize and debate these statements. They were invited to “match” their top three priority statements (Table VI) to existing survey items, and to explore the statements’ meaning in the context of the survey results.

Table VI. Top three priority statements selected by NanoSAFE '23 workshop participants

1. Understanding and acceptance of SSbD by companies needs to be facilitated.
2. SSbD should enhance public involvement through comprehensible and applicable approaches for all stakeholders including the general population.
3. Current development of the socio-economic side of SSbD may not be sufficient to facilitate its implementation.

Key takeaways included:

- Social and responsible research is a central, universal challenge.
- SSbD broadens nanotechnology and advanced materials perspectives beyond materials and chemical processes to include human aspects, such as working conditions, foreign labor, and ethical considerations.
- There are significant challenges related to the activation of an SSbD mentality early in education, industry-wide understanding, and the incorporation of climate considerations – on an equal footing with profit-centered considerations.
- Professionals must communicate about SSbD with stakeholders including the broader public, using appropriate language and action recommendations for each sphere, so that the approach becomes a standard reference in society.

3.5.3 SAbyNA 42-Month Consortium Meeting

Survey data and preliminary advanced statistical treatments were presented under the title of “*SSbD as a cultural fact*”, at the SAbyNA project 42-month consortium meeting held in Grenoble, Oct. 2023. Some 20 colleagues representing the range of project activities (from hazard and exposure assessment through industrial applications to platform development and dissemination) participated in interpreting the data graphics handouts, including preliminary factor analyses examining sectoral trends in free association data (not reported here). Because the colleagues know each other well and have collaborated on multiple dimensions of operationalizing SSbD, the discussion was particularly wide ranging and candid. Some regretted that a longer period of the meeting could not be devoted to examining the RRI study data.

Regarding the free associations to “Sustainability” and linked categories, the following insights were heard:

- The strong linkages seen may be related to “our media environment in Europe. Even if you are not a researcher or come from involved industries, you have on TV or social media these terms that tie together; *eco-friendly* is a label that is often used with the happy word *sustainable*. It’s like a social stereotype.”
- The predominance of *circularity* associations “somehow is also a reply about safety: clearly, if you produce a material that includes toxic substances or legacy additives that in 20 years will not be recovered by recycling, eliminating these upstream is a smart option as compared to lower emissions.”

We quote some reflections offered by participants on certain topical statements. Their comments are not to be taken as conclusions, but rather as interpretations to be discussed in the SSbD forum:

- *SSbD will require lots of changes in industrial processes*: the 67% agreement may reflect a mosaic of different attitudes. “Many in industry think that implementing SSbD will be costly and difficult while the academics and scientists hope there will be a lot of changes... they want an improvement and say ‘yeah, we are going to do things in a different way’. So, yes, many agree that there will be a big change. Some hope so, and others fear the investment they have to face.”
- *SSbD is revolutionary* (high dispersion item): “You could both agree and disagree to some questions like this one. SSbD is not new because it’s been a lot of work over years to develop it. But also, the good changes SSbD introduces means it is revolutionary. So, what do you say?”
- *SSbD will not hinder innovation* (reversed item; 75% consensus). “The general trend of people is to say ‘no, it’s going to be fine.’ Looking at the other strongly agreed items together, it seems that much of the community says: ‘Even if I’m not able to defend SSbD on everything measured by these items, I’m still really confident and ready to defend SSbD on many aspects.’”

The SAbyNA discussants also remarked that the self-selected sample is probably biased in favor of SSbD. In particular, the industry respondents may be those who are highly committed to the approach. Finally, discussants queried whether differences in responses, which are not attributable to finely detailed discipline or to sector, might reflect a generational effect. They pointed out that younger professionals are entering an environment already largely focused on SSbD. Also, the youth milieu, and the profile of their studies, probably trend towards a strong cultural awareness of the green transition and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

3.5.4 JRC/PARC SSbD Bootcamp

A particularly interesting opportunity was offered to SAbyNA by the officials of the EC Joint Research Centre (JRC). We developed a short RRI workshop for a training co-organized by JRC and the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC). The SSbD Bootcamp (Ispra, Italy, 25-27 Oct. 2023) initiated 32 talented young professionals of different disciplines to the SSbD Framework developed by JRC. SAbyNA was invited¹⁴ to close the workshop by creating a participative reflection on interdisciplinarity and on the Bootcamp

¹⁴ The Bootcamp was held face to face but C. Mays (Symlog) facilitated the workshop session at a distance through Webex.

experience. In collaboration with SSbD Project Officer Irantzu Garmendia Aguirre both a workshop evaluation questionnaire and a special Bootcamp edition of several survey questions were prepared. The survey questions were in fact considerably modified to respond to Bootcamp needs. Replying to this mini-survey prior to coming to Ispra, participants were asked during the workshop to compare their own perceptions to similar topics assessed by the larger SAbyNA survey. Moreover, the participants were initiated to aspects of social science methodology including content analysis and interpretation of factor analysis. With reference to the theory of social representations which posits that specialist knowledge eventually disseminates (often through the media) to become popular knowledge, Bootcampers generated “headlines” for society at large about today’s SSbD activity.

Mindful of the pitfalls of comparing data from non-identical questionnaires and samples of very different size, we developed specific assessment exercises for the Bootcamp. Using factor analysis (not reported in this deliverable) we identified several polarized conceptual clusters in the SAbyNA free associations (see section 3.3). The pre-workshop questionnaire asked participants to select the cluster that best aligns with their personal conception of SSbD, or, of Sustainability. Figure 14 displays the respective replies.

Figure 14. Conceptual cluster best aligned with JRC/PARC Bootcamp participants’ personal conception of SSbD or of Sustainability.

For Safety by Design, the Bootcampers selected the outstanding combined categories Environmental/ Human Health & Safety, followed by Anticipation/Prevention. This represents a slight reversal of the free association categories prioritized by the larger SAbyNA survey but aligns with the strongest consensus statement on the health benefits to be expected from SSbD. (No Bootcamper selected the cluster “*Socioeconomics/ Industry/ Costs/ Responsibility*” as best aligned with their understanding of SSbD.)

For Sustainability, the field is hugely dominated by themes that would be grouped in our final SAbyNA analysis as *Circularity* ideas, whereas footprint and eco-friendly concerns came in a poor second. This is an interesting datum from a population well-versed in life cycle analysis, as many Bootcampers were. It suggests that there might be room to dialogue with other SSbD actors to develop mutual understanding of the different priorities reflected in alignment with the operational circular paradigm vs. eco-sensibility and resource/impact concerns.

Topical statements were specifically developed for the Bootcamp. Participants evaluated these before the training (N=32) on a five-point scale ranging from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree.” Figure 15 displays largely consensual replies.

Figure 15. Topical statements about SSbD developed for the JRC/PARC Bootcamp; participants' agreement or disagreement (N=32; frequencies).

The right side of Fig. 15 highlights Bootcamp participants' unanimous belief in the positive utility of SSbD. They are particularly convinced that SSbD will have a positive impact on safety and security of chemicals, materials and products. This perception can be generally compared with the SAbYNA survey consensus on SSbD's expected positive impact on ecosystem health (92%) or occupational health and worker safety (90%).

Items assessing familiarity (top left) indicate that the candidates accepted to the Bootcamp considered themselves well prepared for their upcoming program. The somewhat greater degree of disaccord regarding the novelty of SSbD approaches may reflect the specific range of disciplinary knowledge brought by the Bootcampers. In any case, feeding back such consensual data, with its nuances, can contribute to building community identity.

4. Conclusions and Perspectives

4.1 Main messages of the SAbyNA survey

The SAbyNA Responsible Research and Innovation survey has delivered a portrait of how 172 engaged experts in the nano communities view Safe and Sustainable by Design in 2023. Spontaneous, top-of-mind ideas are clearly focused on the preventive, pro-active nature of the approach to assure safety (lead category: *Anticipation & Risk Control*). *Materials & Processes* are linked in mind with such anticipatory design. The strategic, holistic approach appears as a driving force to achieve integrative *One Health* outcomes.

The expert community we consulted indeed is unified around a massive expectation that “*the application of SSbD will make a positive impact on the health of the environment/environmental health,*” and a hope only slightly less confident that “*worker safety/occupational health*” will benefit positively as well. The community is firmly convinced that “*if we don't pay the costs of implementing SSbD today, we will pay for shortcomings in the future.*” These experts are highly committed, being “*personally all in favor of SSbD.*”

Together the experts strongly affirm that “*SSbD induces a new mentality,*” and they express the need for “*decision support tools to help implement SSbD.*” The community is still bound by consensus in strongly considering that the application of SSbD “*won't hinder innovation.*” However, visions of actual requirements on the factory floor are less cohesive. While a majority admit that “*SSbD will require lots of changes in industrial processes,*” the consensus is less emphatic.

The stability of views in the community decreases again when considering specifics of applying SSbD and its impacts. A large proportion of potential swing votes – ideas that could evolve either way – emerges as to whether “*current technology has enough predictive power to enable SSbD strategy,*” whether “*it will be difficult to apply SSbD without diminishing functionality and/or performance*” or become “*harder for industry to meet economic objectives.*” Broad dissensus – i.e. dispersion of opinion – is seen regarding the application of SSbD at production level. Will SSbD “*add undue costs*”? Will processes in some industrial sectors prove “*incompatible with an SSbD strategy*”? Is it necessary that SSbD costs be “*more quantified*” before the approach can be judged? The community provides no clear answers here.

Socio-economic issues and questions thus come clearly into view. This domain is present in top-of-mind ideas, and especially in the additional comments that certain respondents took care to write. Whether focused on industry applications or larger societal responsibilities, socio-economic themes are cited as relevant to both anticipating safety and achieving sustainability. Nonetheless, at present the environmental pillar of sustainability stands out most clearly in the SSbD community. Sustainability appears dominated in our experts' minds by references to *Eco-friendliness* and concerns for the anthropogenic *Carbon Footprint*. Sustainability appears primarily to mean applying the *Circular* paradigm and strategies to promote healthy ecosystems, and also to reduce harmful emissions and impacts.

Kelty (2009) asked “which kind of concerns, exactly, will be synthesized into a mode of control of matter” as the “story of safety by design” in nanotechnology unfolds. He wondered whether these would be “concerns over safety and risk, or concerns for energy efficiency, cost or profitability” (p80). The SAbyNA RRI survey of 2023 shows that all these concerns are integrated in the vision of Safe and Sustainable by Design. As mindful efforts coalesce at European and international levels to operationalize SSbD, each dimension is taken into account, with more or less maturity, and the fact of a “*change in mentality*” is acknowledged even if SSbD is not clearly considered to be “*revolutionary*.”

4.2 An expanding cultural dynamic

We framed our study of SSbD using the theory of social representations (Moscovici 2001; Bauer & Gaskell 2008). This concept points to the potentially shared nature of ideas and practices, and the way groups construct these together to define and support their community.

Our survey results summarized above indicate that some shared ideas about SSbD are very strong. These dominant consensus views can be labeled social representations. They reflect the identity and beliefs of the engaged SSbD community who decided to respond to our questionnaire. The message uniting the community – independently, it seems, of discipline or sector – is that SSbD is a necessary, positive strategy that will improve the health of the environment/our environmental health, and improve occupational safety. Together, members of the community are strongly committed to SSbD and engaged in the change in mentality. They call for tools and resources to operationalize SSbD.

These and other elements of today’s SSbD social representation are interesting signs of an enthusiastic dynamic of development. This is a community that is bound together by a common action goal, and its associated values in favor of chemicals/nanosafety and sustainability. The fruits of thinking and acting together are evident in the objective scientific and industrial progress in SSbD tools and frameworks. Moreover, our comparison of 2021 and 2023 survey data gives insight into precise ways that SSbD has progressed in the minds of community members. Top-of-mind ideas coalesce and are more strongly linked with a greater variety of ideas. In the two-year period of rapid institutional drive for SSbD, there are thus many signs that collective construction of meaning has taken place. Participants in this cultural nexus have broadened and deepened their understanding of the SSbD concept, elaborated some of its implications, and exchanged more and more with each other on these subjects. Combined with the fact that these community members share adherence to the scientific method, always seeking to objectify and verify understandings, **such a cultural dynamic of building shared representations is a great strength for reaching the goals of SSbD.**

Events and exchanges within the community may have been a key element in this dynamic. Typically, the diverse stakeholders of SSbD – in the lab, the field, the factory or boardroom, the halls of government or the conference hall – mindfully engage in exchanging scientific and practical information. They work together to create enlightened strategies. The SAbyNA survey data can be offered to the community as complementary information to help advance this joint work. Feeding back both consensual data and the nuances of dissensus can contribute to building community identity and to setting action roadmaps.

Such feedback has been our team’s modest contribution in the context of several workshops.

Importantly, our workshops took place within events focused on interdisciplinarity, which is recognized by the community as a vital feature of implementing SSbD. The survey feedback provided a supplementary way to grasp interdisciplinarity, through checking the diversity of views and understandings. According to participants' comments in Venice and Grenoble, this feedback exercise also renewed awareness of the need to expand communication about SSbD beyond an inner sphere or a single stakeholder sector.

The openness to feedback and communication supports the nano/advanced materials community's focus on an inclusive interdisciplinary approach to promote safety and sustainability. It confirms the "willingness of stakeholders to work together toward social[ly] desirable products" (von Schomberg 2013, p29). It aligns with the 2022 CSS High-level Roundtable insight that "cooperation is essential as SSbD requires a collective effort and collaborative learning, and an exchange of best practices. This necessitates a clear (cultural) paradigm shift among all stakeholders."¹⁵

Box 6. Interdisciplinarity and dialogue between stakeholders play a unifying and inspiring role for the implementation/culture of Safe and Sustainable by Design. The complexity of the issues surrounding the safety and sustainability of nanomaterials calls for an integrated approach, bringing together diverse expertise from fields such as materials science, toxicology, ethics, sociology, and economics. Interaction between these disciplines promotes a holistic understanding of the implications of SSbD. Open and continuous dialogue between stakeholders, including scientists, industrialists, regulators, and civil society, enables a diversity of perspectives and experiences to be incorporated. This contributes to the development of more robust standards and practices, aligned with the expectations and values of the European society as a whole. Interdisciplinarity and dialogue thus reinforce the legitimacy and effectiveness of SSbD approaches, fostering more responsible implementation that is adapted to the needs and concerns of all stakeholders.

At their October 2022 workshop (Furxhi et al. 2023) European project leaders and institutional stakeholders found that (public) communication could be an easily workable answer to the high-priority, high-difficulty challenge of translating scientific knowledge into an SSbD decision-making process. They viewed that such communication requires establishing a common language and terminology across disciplines and sectors, "harmonized, clear and precise" as Gottardo et al. (2017) earlier called for. **Specific willingness to communicate is another strength for the SSbD community.**

Cooperation, collaborative learning, and communication are needed to address pragmatic scientific and industrial questions and transfer knowledge between these spheres into decision making. They can be enhanced by a process of dialogue around background beliefs and representations, both consensual and less settled.

¹⁵ Quoted in Furxhi et al. (2023) from the 3rd meeting of the EU High-level Roundtable on the Chemicals Strategy For Sustainability, Brussels, Belgium, 2022-05-18. <https://webcast.ec.europa.eu/3rd-meeting-of-the-high-level-roundtable-on-the-chemicals-strategy-for-sustainability>.

4.3 Dialogue and guidance for SSbD progress

The SAbyNA RRI survey revealed areas in which social representations are not strongly fixed. How can such data serve the community? These areas of uncertainty correspond mainly to the actual implementation of SSbD in industrial contexts, and the impacts that will be felt, including at the level of costs. **These are aspects for which further dialogue, operationalization, and guidance are needed in order to effectively apply SSbD. They are also aspects for which some objective guidance does exist and where stakeholders can be given more foresight.** These aspects should be mindfully examined and debated in the next development period. Certain survey items could usefully be brought into community discussion, to dialogue about the manifest uncertainties, and reinforce the joint dynamic already underway to reduce them.

The SAbyNA guidance platform addresses certain of these problematic aspects directly. Stakeholders could join a cross-sector workshop to debate the weakest survey consensus items: *“I have a good overall understanding of how SSbD at my own level impacts other parts of the value chain,”* and *“SSbD will require lots of changes to industrial processes.”* They could examine the divergent and unclear views on SSbD’s costs and impacts. This dialogue could be followed immediately by a hands-on learning application of the SAbyNA online tool. Indeed, the **SAbyNA guidance platform delivers quantified, operational replies to questions on the costs and requirements of improving safety and sustainability, through comparing detailed nano/advanced materials, product or process scenarios.** The SAbyNA platform provides to industrial stakeholders (particularly in the nano-enabled paints and additive manufacturing sectors) **a tailored response to the still-unclear issues of the magnitude of costs potentially added by SSbD, and the compatibility of the approach** within their production environment.

Our survey confirmed the recognition that socio-economic themes are less settled in the consulted community. The EC Recommendation (2022) establishing an SSbD framework explicitly stated:

“The review of safety and sustainability dimensions, aspects, methods, indicators and tools, that is the root of [the proposed draft framework], although referring to a number of additional socio-economic sustainability aspects, focuses mainly on chemical safety and environmental sustainability. Assessments of socio-economic aspects, beyond those considered already, may be necessary in order to provide additional information and enable more informed decisions, in particular when promoting substitution.” (§13, p.3)

Rising to the need to broaden sustainability considerations, SAbyNA guidance (like that developed by other NMBP-15 and NMBP-16 SSbD projects) integrates classical and new socio-economic assessment tools. Such tools typically address economic costs, time spent, and e.g. ethical profile of resource provision (child labor or environmental impacts). Operationalization of sustainability will doubtless continue in the SSbD community. Here too the SAbyNA RRI survey data could offer a useful basis for dialogue and consolidation. The broad range of sustainability images, and specifically socio-economic ideas and commentary, provided by our respondents could trigger dialogue on how stakeholders diversely conceptualize and prioritize in this area.

4.4 Future prospects: benchmarking and systematic research

Our starting hypothesis, rooted in our own (Bertoldo et al. 2026; Hardy & Mays 2022) and many other authors' earlier work, was that primary discipline might be an important influence in perceptions and attitudes regarding SSbD. This hypothesis has not been borne out at the present stage of survey analysis. A new round of analysis with more sophisticated tests (to be reported in a future peer-reviewed article) will consider new disciplinary groupings, examine other demographic variables, and identify other internal relations in the data.

Nonetheless, the SAbyNA Responsible Research and Innovation study, using empirical social psychology methods, was focused less on explaining relations of influence, and more on offering a reflexive opportunity. We wanted to take a meaningful snapshot of a fast-evolving set of meanings and practices, at a period marked by broad and rapid, mindful development of the SSbD approach. At the present time, our survey results are useful because they can spark ideas and dialogues by participants in this dynamic, and highlight areas where guidance can and must provide pragmatic responses. In this way, the SAbyNA RRI study seeks to enrich the current discourse on SSbD and promote a supportive context for innovation and interdisciplinarity.

The SAbyNA survey results also have a future value. A. Rip (2006) provocatively described “folk theories of nanotechnologists” as searches for pattern yielding untested projections of how nanomaterials would be received in society. He characterized folk theory as exempt from systematic checking. Making views on SSbD an object of systematic research, as we have done, creates an opportunity for reflexive exploration. Our comparison of 2021 and 2023 data furnished some specific insights that may not have emerged at a single-time assessment. Looking forward, the SAbyNA social representations survey contributes a **baseline** to measure the evolution of expert views and practices across future years.

The theory of social representations suggests that the dynamic creating a shared understanding and operationalization of SSbD could eventually largely influence the ways European or other publics represent nanotechnologies and advanced materials. The specialist work to make chemicals safer and more sustainable can eventually become part of general culture, and shape expectations and behavior by consumers. The SAbyNA survey image of experts' understanding of SSbD at today's point in time may also be of use when later, the eventual uptake by broader society of ideas about Safe and Sustainable by Design is traced and assessed.

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Annex: The SAbyNA Responsible Research and Innovation questionnaire on social representations of Safe and Sustainable by Design

SAbyNA RRI Questionnaire on social representations of Safe and Sustainable by Design © 2023 by Hardy S, Karatchodjoukova F, Bertoldo R, Mays C, is licensed under **Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International** (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0). To view a copy of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>.

Part One – Evocation Task

[For this section, a minimum of two responses was required, but four separate response fields were provided. Each of the three questions was offered on a separate screen.]

1. What are the first words/ideas that come to mind when you hear the term **Safe by Design**? (50 character limit)

Minimum: 2 responses, but we invite you to provide up to 4.

2. What are the first words/ideas that come to mind when you hear the term **Sustainability**? (50 character limit)

Minimum: 2 responses, but we invite you to provide up to 4.

3. Are you aware of/knowledgeable about SSbD resources and/or guidance tools? (Yes/No)

- 3b. [If yes:] Please indicate a few of the resources, or types of resources, you are thinking of: [free response field]

Part Two – Agree/Disagree

How much do you agree with these statements on "Safe and Sustainable by Design" (SSbD)?

[Possible responses: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Somewhat Disagree, Somewhat Agree, Agree, Strongly Agree, No opinion/Don't Know, Not Applicable to My Situation.]

[Questions were displayed in blocs. Statement presentation was randomized, bloc order was not. Responses were required for all.]

Bloc One

- I am quite familiar with current SSbD concepts.
- I have an overall understanding of how SSbD at my level impacts other parts of the value chain.
- I would like a decision support tool to help implement SSbD.
- I know who to turn to in my work environment to discuss SSbD approaches.

Bloc Two

- SSbD induces a new mentality.
- SSbD is very different from current safety approaches.
- SSbD is revolutionary.

Bloc Three

- SSbD requirements will hinder innovation.
- The application of SSbD will make a positive impact on worker safety/occupational health.
- The application of SSbD will make a positive impact on the health of the environment/environmental health.
- SSbD will make it harder for industry to meet economic objectives.

Bloc Four

- Community events are a major resource for understanding and developing SSbD.
- My workplace is interested in implementing SSbD with or without external requirements to do so.
- I am personally all in favor of SSbD.
- The organizations promoting or developing SSbD don't understand my needs.

Bloc Five

- SSbD will add undue costs.
- If we don't pay the costs of implementing SSbD today, we will pay for shortcomings in the future.
- SSbD will require lots of changes in industrial processes.
- I need SSbD costs to be more quantified before I judge the approach.

Bloc Six

- There may be industrial sectors whose processes are incompatible with an SSbD strategy.
- It will be difficult to apply SSbD without diminishing functionality and/or performance.
- Current technology has enough predictive power to enable SSbD strategy.

[After completing the blocks, participants were asked the following question:]

(Optional) After agreeing/disagreeing with the statements above, is there a statement we missed? Which statement would YOU add to this questionnaire?

[free response field]

Part Three – Demographics

1. What is your primary field of training? [free response field]
2. Is the discipline of your current field of work the same as your primary field of training? (Yes/No)
 - 2b. If yes, please indicate the main discipline of your current field of work. [free response field]
3. Select the sector of activity that best describes your role:
 - a. Academia
 - b. Consultancy
 - c. Industry

- d. Regulation
 - e. Policy
 - f. Research & Technical Support
 - g. Other: (Open response)
4. Country in which you work: [free response field]
5. Gender: [free response field]
6. What is your current level of schooling?
- a. Up to and including undergraduate
 - b. Master's student
 - c. Master's degree
 - d. Doctoral student
 - e. Doctorate
 - f. Post-doctorate
7. Please choose all relevant options: I am directly involved in:
- a. Nanoform/Advanced materials design or production
 - b. Nanoform characterization
 - c. Hazard assessment
 - d. Fate/exposure assessment
 - e. Substance registration
 - f. Nanoenabled product design or production
 - g. Regulation
 - h. Distribution/retail
 - i. Consumer use
 - j. End of life disposal/recycling
 - k. Other: (Open response)
 - l. Not applicable
8. Are you or have you been involved in a government-sponsored project on nanosafety?
(Yes/No)

